

METHODS THAT AFFECT THE INCREASE IN CREATIVITY OF ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: *the article begins which provides information on the factors that increase the creativity of students in the classroom and the technologies that can be used in the educational process.*

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The social activity of members of society is determined by their scientific potential and scientific worldview. The economic, political, social and cultural prosperity of the developed states in the current period is closely related to the development of science. In such a system, the issue of teaching the younger generation to independent and creative thinking becomes of particular importance. Because reforms in the field of education not only serve to train qualified personnel, but are also aimed at developing the scientific potential of civil society.

Today, fundamental reforms in the field of education are being carried out in our independent republic. In the "National program of Personnel Training "it is stated that" reconstruction of the system and content of Personnel Training is envisaged, based on the prospects for the social and economic development of the country, the needs of society, modern achievements of science, culture, technology and technology." The demand of today's era lies in the work of pedagogical personnel serving to increase the education of the country and the fruits of their work – the education of the younger generation of educated, resourceful, hardworking, devoted youth to the motherland. Since the task of the educator is to educate and educate the younger generation, it is impossible to achieve this goal without necessarily instilling students' interest in science, increasing their activity and ensuring that they receive more information. The activity of students is primarily influenced by the process of their entry into motivation. Education is a collaborative activity of teachers and students, in the process of which the development of the individual, his

education and upbringing also takes place. In classes, the teacher conveys his knowledge, skills and abilities to students through training, while students, as a result of mastering it, acquire the ability to use it.

In the process of learning, students use various manifestations of assimilation, that is, rely on specific differences in the reception, processing and implementation of the information being assimilated into practice. In the educational process, the issues of cooperation of teachers and students during classes, independent work of students, education and upbringing in the form of extracurricular activities are resolved.

Motivation is the sum of various reasons that motivate a person to study or perform an action, and education and upbringing are of great importance to achieving a high result. One of the factors affecting the activity of pupils is stimulation. A clear understanding of the shortcomings and achievements of students in the educational process is a clear basis for a positive result. Therefore, the reader is encouraged when he has achieved an achievement, such as praise, exemplifying, giving gifts, while in negative situations, on the contrary, a reprimand is needed. When praise, used in its place and correctly, increases confidence in the reader in his own strength, then a reproach pronounced in his place will prevent a negative state. But, being aware of the psychology of the pedagogical child, one should attach importance to the fact that even excessive praise causes a negative state in the reader's psyche.

The next factor affecting the reader's attitude to reading, interest is the family environment. The attitude towards the child in the family, interest in science, encouragement, need timely reprimand, setting constant tasks in the House, establishing a system of age-appropriate requirements affect students on the path of future development. A wide outlook, high spirituality, responsibility of the parents must in many ways serve as an example for the child, only then the child will always be active in school, ready to master knowledge.

Another factor that increases creativity is the effective use of innovative educational technologies, interactive techniques. In general, a child who is not interested in anything is not in the world, he can only be a teacher who cannot be interested. Therefore, the pedagogue is obliged to constantly find ways to influence his activity by himself, using new methods. For example, interest in nature, interest in the human body is never outdated, questions of interest to children often begin in this area. Various role-playing games, phenomena related to nature, flora and fauna, using organs in a person, can be closely connected with the lessons being

taught. Especially a child who is going to elementary school is interested in understanding the world. When giving them knowledge, riddles, parables, folk tales are best used, they are kept in mind longer. After all, - it is not for nothing that the knowledge learned in youth is a pattern carved on a stone. A child in the upper class feels like an adult, in which the parents, the teacher, the neighborhood must influence together to support him and realize that adults will never be ashamed if they become more aware. Having given the reader the most interesting information from the inside of a topic, it is imperative to create conditions for the continuation to be read by the child himself, to receive an independent education, and if we can influence the aspiration of the book itself as to what is left, we will achieve the goal. A child taught by independent reading differs from others in that he keeps in mind the meaning and content of the work he has read even over the years. Especially in this, the role of the teacher is extremely large, enriching and stimulating the student with interesting information when giving an independent assignment further slows down his desire for knowledge. In conclusion, the student's creativity – increases the level of the lesson, ensures that the lesson –live. Even, when sometimes, he forces the teacher to seek. Therefore, every pedagogue should first of all work on himself, and then use the opportunity he has in raising the younger generation, and be able to see the prospects with those young people who raise him.

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